

Impact of Photojournalism on Readers' Exposure and Retention: A Study on Cognitive Level of Bangladeshi Audience

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***Abstract:** Since our world is so connected these days, growth of digital devices, news, and media organizations will pay a high premium for the greatest and most interesting photographs available. As events unfold, it's easy to feel cynicism and skepticism. Word travels fast, and many search for the most trustworthy and reliable sources of information. Photojournalists are present, alongside more traditional journalists, to create a story that speaks for itself. Using the qualitative research method, this study primarily focuses on the social cognition theory to demonstrate the effect of photojournalism on readers' exposure and retention. The purpose of this research is to show that visual aids like photographs can significantly improve memory retention. The visual aid greatly increases the chances of remembering what was read. Images that aren't directly associated with the text tend to be forgotten quickly. In this study, social cognition theory is applied to the people of Chattogram to determine the optimal conditions for maximizing reader engagement and knowledge retention focusing on the cognitive level of the audiences. This research also demonstrates the wide variety of quick-read news stories available in visual formats. Pictures in the news need to be just the right size to keep the attention of the readers. 150 people from the general public aged between 18-30 were chosen for this study and three renowned newspapers from both online and offline modes (Daily Ittefaq, The Daily Star, and Bdnews24.com) were selected for gathering data. Research results lend considerable credence to social cognition arguments.*

***Keywords:** Social cognition theory, Photojournalism, Readers' exposure and retention, Impact of the picture*

Introduction

A photograph is a piece of photographic film or an electronic image sensor.

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10% of what people hear is remembered, 20% of what they read is remembered, and 80% of what they see is remembered. We understand what an image says in 13 milliseconds (less than a blink of an eye!) because visuals are processed 60,000 times faster than words (Wanta,1988). 90% of the information we take in is visual. The power of an image is mainly: the power to attract, persuade and sell (Mendelson, 2001). Photojournalism may be a branch of photography that uses photos or images to inform a story (Gilbert et al., 1990). Editors use photos to shape public opinion because they know people are more likely to read and pay attention to stories that include images (Gibson et al., 2000).

Photographic journalism is a contemporary form of news medium. It entails making images associated with news events so that the audience can have a clearer understanding of what's going on. One definition of photojournalism is "the practice of reporting news visually." As photographs began to bring events to life, they made the events more relevant to the viewer, expanding the reach of photojournalism (Coleman et al., 2004). The power of photography to influence public opinion was recognized, and efforts were made to do so on topics ranging from politics to international affairs (Arpan et al., 2009). Photojournalists are in high demand around the world because of the vital role they play in illustrating news reports. Together, these improvements make it easier to read the newspaper and watch the news, make connections between the news and real life, and gain a more complete understanding of what it must have been like to be there at that time and place (Barrett et al., 2005). Photojournalism refers to the art of reporting using visual media, such as photographs and videos.

A photojournalist may also engage in the activity of photojournalism. It's easy to remember the noun, but it's much harder to keep track of the corresponding actions. Taking the picture that best illustrates the story, the photojournalist makes the picture the story (Prabu, 1998). Even if it's just a camera phone, almost everyone these days can take photos. As a direct consequence of this, an increasing number of eyewitness reports of events are being documented by individuals who just so happened to be in the appropriate place at the appropriate moment.

The term "exposure" refers to the act of experiencing something or the disclosure of a previously unknown fact. Contrarily, retention refers to one's mental capacity to remember something (Morrison et al., 2012). How long an audience remembers stories and news stories is known as "media retention" (Barma et al., 2003). In contrast, the photojournalism concept of reader exposure and retention (also known as reader engagement) quantifies how compelling your story is to the intended audience. In this episode, we compare how many people begin reading your story to how many people make it to the end of each chapter. When more people read to the end of each chapter, your retention rate improves.

Bandura's theory of social cognition is one of the most influential and well-known in all of social psychology. It has had an effect on a number of sectors, including communication and, in particular, the study of the consequences of photojournalism. The Social Cognitive Theory (SCT), which is utilized in the fields of psychology, education, and communication, postulates that certain aspects of a person's knowledge acquisition are frequently directly associated with observing other people within the context of social interactions, experiences, and influences from the outside media (Bandura, 1989). The social theory of mind provides support for the idea that a single image can drastically alter the significance of news and the interest level of readers (Chesebro et al., 1996). Because of its profound impact on the minds of its readers, the social cognitive theory is used here.

The main motivation for this research was an interest in gaining a deeper comprehension of the part that graphics play in contemporary journalism. An image can freeze time, preserving memories of a special occasion or a priceless moment (Bruder, 2007). These days, just about everyone always has some kind of camera on them, be it a mobile phone, a digital camera, a tablet, etc. Everyone is now a photographer because of this. A common reason why people take pictures is so they can look back on meaningful moments in their lives (Grey, 2007). Also, since people tend to remember and trust what they see, photographs in print media are crucial to the memorization process. The goals of the study were developed with this conversation in mind:

- Find out what ratio of text-to-image size maximizes readers' ability to retain information and illustrate how people react to news articles that

don't include pictures.

- Create a connection between the images associated with news stories and the reader's ability to remember those stories later and to learn whether readers prefer news articles with or without accompanying visuals.
- To acknowledge the role of photography in news reporting as a significant factor in readers' ability to remember particular stories.

Materials and Methods

Data and Methodology:

In this research, an experimental strategy was used. Scientists use experiments to identify and characterize important variables (Radder H.,2009). The research's aims, requirements, and character informed the decision to use this approach. In this study, the photo retention rates of three different news sources (the Daily Ittefaq, the Daily Star, and bdnews24.com) were compared. Each of these newspapers features the same generic headlines and article content. 150 people were asked to fill out a survey about how photojournalism affects readers' attention and recall. Google Forms were used to create the survey's structure, and respondents were given access via email.

Research Questions:

In order to achieve the goals of the study, the following research questions were developed:

- How do photos in news articles affect people's ability to remember what they read?
- How do irrelevant photos affect people's ability to remember news stories?
- How much do readers forget when there are no photos to go along with the text?
- In what ways do photos play a role in the selection of news stories?
- When it comes to inside coverage, how well do people remember the news?
- Does the size of a photo matter in choosing news?

Data Collection Procedures:

Data collection is a way of gathering and analyzing data on specific factors to aid in the analysis and answering pertinent issues (Kishan Hari et al., 2021). This study uses a structured questionnaire as its survey instrument. Questionnaires help to save the researcher's time and cost (Bucher et al., 2006). As discussed above there are three sorts of newspapers. The 50 students all receive a copy of the newspaper. The researcher uses experimental methods on a sample of 150 Chattogram respondents. A simple random sampling strategy is used to select the sample. By using this experimental method, the researcher was able to determine the extent to which news stories are remembered (Stenberg, 2006). People who were accessible, centrally located, interested in taking part, and had time to answer questionnaires were contacted in order to collect information.

Data Analysis:

The term "data analysis" refers to the methodical examination and organization of information gathered from a specific research topic in order to answer a specific research question. Researchers use research data analysis to distill data into a meaningful narrative and draw conclusions. Data analysis solves research questions by searching and organizing field data and other materials. Data analysis checked the research instrument for completeness and errors. Study questions categorize the data. Themes are created by organizing data by instrument goals. Survey data is examined for study relevance. This study uses solely qualitative data to measure values in terms of frequency. Qualitative data analysis identifies, analyzes, and interprets textual patterns and themes to answer research questions.

Result

This chapter provides data analysis and a presentation of the results of the study. The findings of this study are presented in tables and figures.

Table 1: Retention of news which includes photographs relate to the text

Newspapers	Maximum Details	Intermediate Details	Minimum Details	Irrelevant Details
Daily Ittefaq	18.5%	21%	33.5%	33.5%
The Daily Star	22.5%	23%	43.5%	16%
Bdnews24.com	48.5%	28.5%	18.5%	7.5%

Interpretation:

In Table 1 only 18.5% of readers of Daily Ittefaq, which does not use any visual aids other than text, retain the maximum amount of information presented in each story. In spite of the fact that The Daily Star frequently uses photos that have nothing to do with the text, 22.5 percent of readers can recall all information presented in the articles. Bdnews24.com's maximum retention rate is 48.5%, while the site's inclusion of contextual images improves readability. Therefore, the information that can be found in newspaper shows can be found in Table 1. The Bdnews24.com website has the highest possible recall for its news stories.

Table 2: Retention of news which includes photographs unrelated to the text

Newspapers	Maximum Details	Intermediate Details	Minimum Details
Daily Ittefaq	17.5%	18.5%	65%
The Daily Star	15.5%	59.5%	27%
Bdnews24.com	47.5%	28.5%	25%

Interpretation:

Table 2 establishes that H2, which often includes photos that have little to do with the text, has a moderate level of recall. On the daily news site Ittefaq, where only text is available, 18.5 percent of readers can recall key details from the story they read a few days ago. Even though Bdnews24.com includes accompanying images that help people remember key details, only 28.5% of people can recall those details. The Daily Star's readers retain a higher percentage of intermediate details about news stories than those of any other newspaper despite the publication's practice of including unrelated photographs with news stories.

Table 3: Retention of news that is purely text

Newspapers	Maximum Details	Intermediate Details	Minimum Details	Unrelevant Details
Daily Ittefaq	15%	15%	17.5%	27.5%
The Daily Star	20%	20%	35%	15%
Bdnews24.com	37.5%	29.5%	20%	15%

Interpretation:

Table 3 demonstrates that the highest percentage of irrelevant data (29.5%) can be found in the Daily Ittefaq, which includes news stories with pure text. When compared to The Daily Star (which features unrelated photos) and Bdnews24.com, that's a significant increase (which includes related photos to news).

Table 4: Images as an important factor in the selection of news stories

Newspapers	Picture	Space	Headline	Interest	Prominent Personality
The Daily Star	28.5%	12.5%	23.5%	29.5%	10%
Bdnews24.com	36%	15%	21%	20%	10%

Interpretation:

The evidence presented in Table 4 demonstrates that photographs are the single most important consideration in the selection of certain news pieces. In the case of The Daily Star includes irrelevant photos 28.5% of individuals selected news stories to be exposed based on photos and Bdnews24.com includes relevant photos for 36%.

Table 5: Retention of inside news stories

Newspapers	Percentage of individuals who don't remember inside news stories
Daily Ittefaq	68.5%
The Daily Star	38.5%
Bdnews24.com	27%

Interpretation:

Table 5 reveals that 68.5% of respondents were unable to recall any of the inside news stories that were related to Daily Ittefaq. 38.5% of The Daily Star readers can't recall key details from recent articles. Only 27% of Bdnews24.com's readers couldn't recall the day's events.

Table 6: Effect of photo size on the selection of news stories

Newspapers	Percentage of news stories which includes perfect size photos
The Daily Star	61.5%
Bdnews24.com	72%

Interpretation:

Table 6 shows that 61.5% of individuals select news stories with perfect size photos related to the text in The Daily Star. When it came to Bdnews24.com, 72% of people chose news stories that had photos that were the ideal size for viewing.

Table 7: Readers' preference to read news with pictures vs without pictures

Newspapers	With Pictures	Without Pictures	Total
Daily Ittefaq	21	14	35
The Daily Star	40	30	70
Bdnews24.com	29	16	45
Total	90	60	150

Interpretation:

Table 7 shows that in total 35 audiences of Daily Ittefaq 21 prefer news with pictures and 14 audiences give priority to the news whether it is with pictures or not. In the case of The Daily Star 40 prefers news with pictures and others prefer without picture news among total 70 audiences and 45 total audiences of Bdnews24.com only 16 prefers to read news without pictures and the remaining 29 prefer to read news with pictures. From the data, it is clear that most audiences like to read news with pictures.

Discussion

Here the experimental approach has been used, as it was the most appropriate for this study. Here the participants for the sample were selected at random and then replaces with them the overall population. The study has a set of corresponding research questions.

The first topic that will be examined in this line of inquiry is, "How much information is preserved when are photographs accompanying news that is related to the text of the news story?" Maximum retention rates are recorded. While less information is retained when the content is deemed inappropriate, such as humorous photos or news articles.

How do pictures that have nothing to do with the news affect people's memories of those stories is the second research question posed. The results indicate that the news is either pertinent or irrelevant to the text. The selection of news stories is now based on photographs.

The amount of information that readers recall after reading news stories that consist just of text is the third area to study. Readers choose and remember the text-only news articles the least. Readers are more likely to remember stories when they include images.

The role that photographs play in the selection of news stories is the subject of our fourth research question. A picture is worth a thousand words when it comes to picking news stories. Photos are the most powerful tools in the selection of news stories, though interest, space, and notable personalities are also important. Because pictures in the news are more interesting to people, more people tend to click on them. Also known as "selective exposure to news stories," this is a common practice. For the simple reason that people only read the news that interests them.

The fifth line of inquiry concerns the extent to which the three distinct types of newspapers remember exclusive news stories. The same amount of information is retained when reading news articles. For example, it has been noted that readers are more likely to remember news stories from newspapers that include photos, whether or not the images are directly related to the text.

When reading the news exclusively via text, readers retain the fewest details. Some people couldn't recall anything about news stories, even when they were read to them.

How the size of photos impacts the selection of news stories is the topic of the sixth research question. Here it can be observed that the size of the accompanying photograph played a significant role in the decision-making process for the selection of news pieces. More photo space in the paper increases the photo's odds of being chosen. The size of the accompanying photograph, then, can selectively affect the amount of information that the reader takes in and remembers.

Photos were found to have the highest rate of information retention, while texts had the lowest (Mendelson et al., 2006). When pictures in the news are unrelated to the text, readers retain some of the stories not all of them. More importantly, the photo is the single most influential factor in a story's visibility. The size of the accompanying photograph plays a crucial role in the editorial process (Kozma, 1991).

Conclusion

We live in a world where technology advances at a breakneck pace, altering the way we interact with content. The new high-tech world has also made us very Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD). We have extremely limited attention spans, and given the quantity of data we are regularly bombarded with, it takes tons to grab our interest. Pictures have a unique ability to instantly register intense emotions in people. They have the facility to impress a good range of feelings: love, fear, thanks, misfortune, etc. Photographs play an increasingly vital role in today's print journalism. People remember things that they see in photos for a long time afterward, and this effect is powerful. The photo also aids in the selection of stories for the reader. Photos are a very effective tool to play up or play down news stories since they can be explored by more readers and will build public opinion on that problem. Photos can also be used to play up or play down news stories. The purpose of this study was to find out whether or not the addition of images improves readers' ability to remember and focus on the material.

This study will shed light on the significance of visuals and images in traditional media. What role do they play in the processes of memorizing and remembering? This study aimed to better understand how photojournalism influences the selection of news stories and how readers remember details from a news article.

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